

Halogenation. Part XIII. Bromination and Iodination of Some Halogenated Benzenes.

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A survey of the literature shows the lack of any systematic study of the direct action of bromine and iodine on partially halogenated benzenes. The bromo and iodo derivatives, which have been prepared before, have generally been done by indirect methods, by replacing the amino group by the halogens. The compounds treated in this paper are *p*-dichlorobenzene, bromo- and *p*-dibromobenzenes and iodobenzene. Direct bromination and iodination of bromobenzene have not been carried out before though the products mentioned here have been obtained by other methods. In the case of *p*-dichlorobenzene, however, 2 : 5-dichloro-1 : 4-dibromobenzene and 3 : 6-dichloro-1 : 2 : 4 : 5-tetrabromobenzene have been prepared before by heating the compound with excess of bromine in presence of iron or AlCl_3 respectively (Wheeler and Mac Farland, *Amer Chem. J.*, 1897, **19**, 366 ; Mouneyrat and Pouret, *Compt. rend.*, 1899, **129**, 1607).

Attempts have been made in this paper to bring about direct bromination and iodination in presence of the following substances : (i) concentrated or fuming nitric acid, (ii) concentrated or fuming sulphuric acid, (iii) a mixture of concentrated sulphuric and nitric acids, or fuming sulphuric and nitric acids, (iv) sodium nitrite and fuming sulphuric acid, and (v) nitrosulphonic acid mixture. The methods adopted are similar to those used in this laboratory for the preparation of the mixed halogen derivatives of toluene and xylene (Varma and others, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 293 ; 1935, **12**, 245).

The experiments carried out with bromo-, dibromo- and iodobenzenes have given satisfactory results. Bromobenzene on bromination gave

p-dibromo and 1 : 2 : 4 : 5-tetrabromobenzenes and on iodination 4-bromo-1-iodobenzene gave 4-bromo-1-iodobenzene and 2 : 5-diiodobenzene. The best yields of the above compounds have been obtained in presence of (a) sodium nitrite and fuming sulphuric acid and (b) nitrosulphonic acid mixture. *p*-Dibromobenzene gave 2 : 5-dibromo-1-iodobenzene with some difficulty.

With *p*-dichlorobenzene it has been possible to obtain the dibromo derivative only. In no case is the monobromo derivative obtainable. An attempt was made to sulphonate the *p*-dichlorobenzene first and then to replace the sulphonic acid group by a bromine atom, but even that proved unsuccessful (*vide* replacement of sulphonic acid groups by nitro groups, Datta and Varma, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 2039; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 321).

EXPERIMENTAL.

In the experiments, tabulated below, the initial compound and bromine were taken together in a round-bottomed flask and heated on a water-bath or a sand-bath under reflux condenser. The halogenating agent was added from the top of the condenser, 1 c. c. at a time at regular intervals. In the case of sodium nitrite and fuming sulphuric acid, sodium nitrite was taken in the flask along with other substances. When the whole mixture had been added, the heating was continued for a further period mentioned against each experiment, and in some cases left to stand for some hours or overnight. The contents were then washed several times with distilled water, and with dilute (1-2%) caustic soda solutions to remove the unreacted halogen. It was finally washed with water and the separated solid was filtered at the pump and recrystallised from a suitable solvent and the m.p. determined. In each case the product was identified by m.p.

In the experiments on iodination, acetic acid was also taken in the flask, as it had been found that it aids iodination considerably. The most important results are summarised in the following table. From the results obtained it is apparent that under the experimental conditions described though the main product is *p*-dibromobenzene from monobromobenzene, a small (almost negligible) quantity of *o*-dibromobenzene is also obtained; but practically no *o*-diiodobenzene is formed on the iodination of monoiodobenzene,

Substance.	Halogen.	Halogenating agent.	Temperature and time.	Product and yield.
p-Dichlorobenzene (10 g.)	Bromine (8 c.c.)	NaNO_2 (12 g.) + fuming H_2SO_4 (15 c.c.)	200°, 4 hrs.	2 : 5-Dichloro-1 : 4-dibromobenzene (m.p. 146°), 4.5 g.
"	"	Nitrosulphonic acid (10 c.c.)	" 6 hrs.	" 4.5 g.
Bromobenzene (5 c.c.)	Bromine (8 c.c.)	NaNO_2 (1 g.) + fuming H_2SO_4 (1 c.c.)	Water-bath for 6 hrs.	p-Dibromobenzene (m.p. 86°) 3.4 g. (negligible quantity of o-dibromobenzene).
"	"	Nitrosulphonic acid (3 c.c.)	" "	" "
p-Dibromobenzene (5 g.)	" (3 c.c.)	" (2 c.c.)	200°, 4 hrs.	1 : 2 : 4 : 5-Tetrabromobenzene (m.p. 185°), 1.3 g.
Iodobenzene (10 c.c.)	" (5 c.c.)	" (5 c.c.)	Water-bath for 4 hrs.	4-Bromo-1-iodobenzene (m.p. 91°) 4.5 g.
Bromobenzene (5 c.c.)	Iodine (10 g.) + acetic acid (10 c.c.)	" (3 c.c.)	" "	" 4.8 g.
"	Iodine (20 g.) + acetic acid (10 c.c.)	NaNO_2 (5 g.) + fuming H_2SO_4 (5 c.c.)	200°, 6 hrs.	" 4.6 g.
p-Dibromobenzene (10 g.)	Iodine (25 g.) + acetic acid (20 c.c.)	Nitrosulphonic acid (10 c.c.)	200°, 42 hrs. and overnight.	2 : 5-Dibrom-1-iodobenzene (m.p. 38°) 1.3 g.
Iodobenzene (10 c.c.)	Iodine (10 g.) + acetic acid (15 c.c.)	NaNO_2 (10 g.) + fuming sulphuric acid (10 c.c.)	200°, 4 hrs.	1 : 4-Diiodobenzene (m.p. 149°), 7 g.
"	"	Nitrosulphonic acid (10 c.c.)	" "	" (5.8 g.)
Diiodobenzene (10 g.)	Iodine (20 g.) + acetic acid (20 c.c.)	Nitrosulphonic acid (15 c.c.)	200°, 6 hrs.	1 : 2 : 4-Triiodobenzene (m.p. 91°), 2.4 g.

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